

Genetic evaluation and utilization

Parijat, a new upland rice variety from India

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Parijat (IET 2684) is a semidwarf rice developed from the cross TN1 /TKM 6 at the Rice Research Station, Bhubaneswar, Orissa. When direct seeded it matures in about 90 days in kharif (wet season) and in 105 days in rabi (dry season). It is suitable for upland areas of the state. Its yield performance in tests of the All India Coordinated Rice

Improvement Project, as well as at the state level in 1972–75, showed its wide adaptability.

Parijat has medium slender grains and field resistance to bacterial leaf blight, bacterial leaf streak, *Helminthosporium* leaf spot, and the green leafhopper, and moderate resistance to the stem borer and the brown planthopper. It is superior to the upland variety Bala in its synchronized flowering and easy threshability. It has better grain quality than the upland rice variety Annapurna (Annapurna has coarse red kernels) and matures about a week earlier. On the average it produces about 3.7 t/ha, with a maximum of 8.2 t/ha under good management. ❧

GENETIC EVALUATION & UTILIZATION

Agromomic characteristics

Rice varieties for late planting in West Bengal

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The vagaries of the southwesterly monsoon in parts of West Bengal often force resowing or delayed planting of rice. During 1975–76, 32 semidwarf high yielding rices (HYV) and 56 tall indigenous cultivars were compared in “optimum” and late plantings. Under rainfed conditions and with identical soil moisture through the growing season, tall indigenous cultivars of early and medium duration proved more tolerant of late planting than the HYV. The superior varieties were N.C. 918 and N.C. 1626 — aus (insensitive) types — and Badkalamkati-7, Jhati, Hiramoti, Churnakati, K X I-36, Basful, Asmanchak, Safadhan, Dudhkalma, Latisail, and Bankura-5-7 — aman (sensitive) types. Their superiority showed in their growth characters, complete panicle exertion, tolerance of bacterial and virus diseases,

and insignificant yield reductions. The mean grain yields were 257 g/sq m from the normal season, 26 July transplanting and 234 g/sq m and 231 g/sq m from late transplantings (10 and 23 September) of seedlings sown 21 August. Most HYV gave higher yields in early sowings, but behaved differently — with incomplete exertion, poor growth, and severe disease, and reduced yield — in late plantings. Mean grain yields were 368 g/sq m, 172 g/sq m, and 108 g/sq m in the normal and the two late plantings, respectively. However, some short-duration HYV, e.g., Pusa 2-21, Pusa 33-30-3-3, IET 2233, IET 1444, and Ratna, performed better. ❧

Flowering of aus rice cultivars in West Bengal, India

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Aus (early) rice cultivars — usually classified as photoperiod insensitive —

were sowed 31 March at Chinsurah, India, permitting exposure to long days for nearly 6 months in the field.

Flowering (50%) time ranged from 60–66 to 123–129 days after sowing. Half of the cultivars flowered between 88 and 94 days. The cultivars collected from a particular area sometimes showed similar flowering dates; sometimes they varied widely (see table). ❧

Collection areas and flowering times of aus rice cultivars. Rice Research Station, Chinsurah, West Bengal, India.

Collection area	Flowering time ^a		
	Early	Medium	Late
West Bengal			
West Dinajpur	4	4	1
Coochbihar	5		
Jalpaiguri	5	4	
Malda	2		
Murshidabad	20	1	
Nadia	30	26	3
24 Paraganas	2	3	
Hooghly	2	4	
Midnapore	2		
Burdwan	6	2	
Birbhum	3		
Bankura	1		1
Purulia		1	
Kashmir	5		1
Manipur			3
East Sikkim			3
Bhutan	1		
USSR	13		
Japan	7	7	4
HW	42	63	3

^aAttainment of 50% flowering: early = 60–87 days; medium = 88–101 days; late = 102–129 days.

Determination of the adaptation of rice genotypes to water deeper than 30 cm — a new formula

A story carrying the above title on page 10 of IRRN 1:2 (DECEMBER 1976) contained an error. Its first paragraph should end as follows:

A scale for interpreting the values classifies the genotypes into four groups: very high (F_D 160 or above), high (F_D 140–159), moderate (F_D 120–139), and low (F_D below 120) adaptation to increasing water depths (see table).